

EDUCATION SYSTEM ABROAD

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Abstract. The article discusses the main global trends in higher education in XXI century. The difference between the domestic and foreign higher education systems. The article provides a general description of modern higher education, lists the trends and prospects for the development of cross-border education. The author considers network interaction as a form of implementing educational programs, which opens up broad prospects for expanding the practice of cooperation between educational organizations and resources to improve the quality of pedagogical education.

Key words: higher education, quality, trends, online education, corporate institution partnerships, International student recruitment, University, electronic training, transnational education, financing of education

Annotatsiya. Maqolada 21-asrda oliy ta'limning asosiy global tendentsiyalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Mahalliy va xorijiy oliy ta'lim tizimlari o'rtasidagi farqlar. Maqolada zamonaviy oliy ta'limning umumiy tavsifi berilgan va transchegaraviy ta'limni rivojlantirish tendentsiyalari va istiqbollari sanab o'tilgan. Muallif tarmoq shovqinini ta'lim dasturlarini amalga oshirish shakli sifatida ko'rib chiqadi, bu o'qituvchilarning ta'lim sifatini oshirish uchun ta'lim tashkilotlari va resurslari o'rtasidagi hamkorlik amaliyotini kengaytirish uchun keng istiqbollarni ochadi.

Kalit so'zlar: oliy ta'lim, sifat, tendentsiyalar, onlayn ta'lim, universitetlarning korporativ hamkorligi, xalqaro talabalarni yollash, universitet, e-learning, transmilliy ta'lim, ta'limni moliyalashtirish

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются основные мировые тенденции высшего образования в XXI веке. Различие отечественной и зарубежной систем высшего образования. В статье дается общая характеристика современного высшего образования, перечисляются тенденции и перспективы развития трансграничного образования. Автор рассматривает сетевое взаимодействие как форму реализации образовательных программ, которая открывает широкие перспективы для расширения практики сотрудничества образовательных организаций и ресурсов для повышения качества педагогического образования.

Ключевые слова: высшее образование, качество, тенденции, онлайн-образование, корпоративное партнерство вузов, международный набор студентов, университет, электронное обучение, транснациональное образование, финансирование образования

Introduction. Nowadays, education is one of the main investments in human capital, and this aspect usually determines a person's ability to compete in the labor market. High quality education is considered the foundation on which a person's well-being and successful career are built. It is very important to choose a good educational institution, after graduating from which the graduate will be able to realize himself to the fullest. According to statistics, every year more and more students go to receive higher education in foreign countries, despite the fact that education is by no means cheap. Thus, foreign universities have a number of distinctive features that attract students from all over the world.

Historically, the domestic and foreign education systems have significant differences, affecting both the academic process and the environment within educational institutions.

It is believed that higher education abroad is primarily focused on identifying and developing the student's natural abilities, and also focuses on the student's self-realization and self-determination. It allows you to more fully take into account the student's interests (he has the opportunity to choose exactly those subjects in which he is interested and which will really be useful).

In addition, independent work and discussion of the material are encouraged, therefore it is believed that education abroad is more liberal than domestic one.

The next distinctive feature of higher education abroad is that in the foreign system more attention is paid to preparing students for the applied use of acquired skills. Our education, unlike foreign ones, devotes little time to methods of applying knowledge in practice, while preparing scientists. Therefore, foreign universities focus on training highly specialized specialists, while our higher education produces generalist specialists. A specialist who has received higher education abroad is qualified in the field in which he is a true professional. If he decides to change his field of activity, he will need to retrain, that is, receive additional education.

An Uzbek specialist has the opportunity to realize himself simultaneously in several related fields of activity, and although he will have extensive knowledge, the specialization of this knowledge is small. Thus, the higher education system abroad makes it possible to prepare qualified narrow-profile specialists, while this higher education is focused on their practical, applied training.

Currently, thanks to international competition, a system of transnational education is developing, which

necessitates the use of specific interstate forms and methods of regulation.

Back in 1995, at the initiative of an international consortium, which included representatives of business and governments of various countries, higher education systems using both traditional and innovative forms and methods of teaching in their work, the Global Alliance for Transnational Education (GATE) was formed, the main goal of which is to provide and improve higher education and professional training that are not bound by the borders of any country.

Carrying out certification in the transnational education sector, GATE seeks to cooperate with national and international structures that ensure the quality of higher education. It uses the methods, approaches and results of internal and external assessments of the activities of higher education institutions obtained by other organizations [1]. For the purposes of our study, it is important that, being a direct result of globalization, transnational education is closely linked to the use of new information technologies and characterizes a real transition to the stage of globalization of educational markets. [7]

The demand for higher education in the world is growing annually by 5-8%, significantly outpacing the services of transnational education. If in 2003, slightly more than 2.0 million students received foreign education in all its forms, then in 2025, 7.2-7.3 million people are expected, a significant part of whom will study under transnational education programs [1]. All this indicates that for the development of an integrated innovative educational environment in Uzbekistan, it is important to know and study the experience of higher education systems in the largest foreign countries

Main part. Several trends in the development of higher education abroad can be identified:

1. Online education

Online education is one of the fastest-growing areas in education technology trends. From 33.1% in 2017, the percentage of all college students who took at least one online class rose to 34.7% the following year. Meanwhile, in the fall of 2020, 97% of college students reported switching to online instruction altogether (Education Data, 2020). With its steady, growing rates, online education remains the main driver of growth in post-secondary enrollments.

Data from various sources reveal that students show a more favorable response to online education. It brings to the table various benefits that cannot be achieved in a traditional classroom setting. For one, it gives students more flexible options, allowing them to take the courses while managing other responsibilities.

These digital learning trends in the higher education sector also signals a good time for learning management systems to expand their market to universities and college institutions.

Because of the recent student demand, there is more emphasis on online learning programs. Online education saw a growth of 15.4% in 2018, up from 14.7% in 2016,

Moreover, it is predicted to increase at a CAGR of 9.23%, reaching \$319.167 billion by 2025.

Diagram 1. Numbers of Internet users worldwide by region, 2015-2020

2. International Student Recruitment

International enrollments are not looking so good for the higher education sector as well. Different institution surveys found that there's a decline in new international enrollments for two years in a row. Despite the higher education sector's efforts in attracting international students, new enrollment rates fell at 5.5% at the graduate level, 6.3% at the undergraduate level, and 9.7% at the non-degree level. Furthermore, due to the pandemic, overall international student enrollment rate has dropped by 16% in 2020.

Educational leaders point to the social and political environment in the US as partly the reason for this decline. The more restrictive policies on US visas and the administration's take on immigration are making it a challenge for higher ed institutions to recruit more international students. With the newest policy in place, international students could easily accrue an unlawful presence in the US and be prohibited from re-entering the US for a period of 3 to 10 years. In addition to these issues, many students have also opted out of studying abroad to avoid the risk of contracting COVID-19.

To battle the declining number of student enrollees, universities and colleges recruit international students more aggressively. Leveraging international student activities can help raise new revenues. Recruiting more international students and encouraging partnerships with universities abroad also raise the stature of colleges and universities to global audiences.

In addition, the recruitment of international students leads to a diversified student body. It allows new cultural contexts that can, when integrated with the current curriculum, better prepare students to compete in a globalized economy.

3. Corporate-Institution Partnerships

Institutions are now working with corporations to ensure that employee skills match their jobs. These enterprise training companies partner with universities and leverage their vast networks to help companies bridge the tech-talent gap in their workforce.

Although the uses of HR solutions include enhancing career development, higher education still serves as a better training ground for students. The likes of Pluralsight and Revature encourage university

partnerships and collaboration with employers. They provide students and companies with the right programs to match their skills and needs.

Pluralsight, an online platform for software and IT developer training, utilizes its industry-updated content. With its close ties with employers, the corporation ensures success in the match. Revature, on the other hand, provides a program where students can pay back their tuition within two years after employment. This way, the needs of both students and employers are addressed through a collaborative learning management process.

International experience in the development of higher education shows that two interrelated processes are taking place: diversification and internationalization of education. Diversification is associated with the organization of new educational institutions, with the introduction of new areas of study, new disciplines and courses, with the creation of interdisciplinary programs, with the assignment of educational functions to public institutions. Internationalization, on the contrary, is aimed at bringing national educational systems closer together, finding and developing common universal concepts and components in them. It should be noted that the right to higher education is realized in almost all countries of the world, not only for citizens of these states, but also for foreign students.

Our country should introduce and formulate clear policies to support the students studying in Uzbekistan, especially in the long-term development plan of the country. The education industry should be regarded as an important part of the agenda. At the same time, because the university evaluation results is an important sign of the level of running a university, the university internationalization level is an important indicator for the evaluation of the international higher education, so our country's higher education evaluation index system should be in line with international standards, the level of internationalization into the evaluation index system, and the number of school students should also be one of the most important as an international index. [7]

Figure 2. Data oriented

Conclusion. The current trends in higher education give us a partial view of what the future has in store for those aspiring to further their education at this level. Some issues need addressing, and actions must be performed for better outcomes. For instance,

technological advancements paved the way for learning management system platforms to address some of the changing demands of the education sector. Developments like this provide more avenues for students and learners to advance their professions.

What's more pressing is how education quality today stands to influence the future workforce. As it is, more corporations are already taking active measures to address employee skill mismatch. By working with educational institutions, corporations provide industry-specific courses to produce highly skilled graduates. This thoughtful matching of courses and industry needs ensures that graduates need not worry about landing jobs for what they spent hours studying for.

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